

CHEWING AND FACIAL MUSCLES

Fayzullayev Baxtiyor

Bukhara University of innovative education and medicine

Abstract: The muscular system of the face is represented by two muscle groups: chewing and mimic. Also, in terms of functionality, they can include a group of muscles that lower the lower jaw, despite the fact that from a topographical point of view such muscles do not belong to the muscles of the face, but are considered as a separate group - the muscles of the bottom of the oral cavity and the upper neck.

Key words: chewing, facial, muscles.

There are 43 muscles on a person's face and head, many of which help us enjoy good food and express our pleasure about it without saying a word.

The chewing muscles give us the ability to open and close our mouths, as well as chew food. The associated musculature allows you to swallow food and drinks.

The muscles responsible for facial expression are located in the jaw area and on the skull: thanks to them, we can carry out non-verbal communication - smile, frown, raise eyebrows in surprise and kiss those who are dear to us.

Chewing function and the muscles responsible for it

Without these muscles, we would have to eat intravenously. Their well-coordinated teamwork allows us to dig into our favorite burger with an appetite and enjoy a cold milkshake.

The four main paired masticatory muscles – the masticatory proper, medial pterygoid, lateral pterygoid and temporal – are attached to the skull and mandible. They are responsible for the movements of the temporomandibular joint.

The buccal and maxillofacial muscles play an auxiliary role in the process of eating and drinking.

Chewing Muscles: These powerful muscles lift your lower jaw so that you can close your mouth and chew food.

One of the strongest facial muscles, the masticatory muscles are very thick, have a flat rectangular shape and are attached to the lower jaw and zygomatic bones on both sides of the face.

Medial pterygoid muscles: These muscles have as many as three functions.

Being also located on both sides of the head, they work as follows:

With simultaneous contraction of both muscles, the lower jaw is pushed forward.

The contraction of one medial pterygoid muscle causes the jaw to move in the opposite direction – this is how we move the jaw left and right.

Thanks to the simultaneous work of the medial pterygoid, masticatory and temporal muscles, we are able to close our mouths and bite.

These muscles are attached to the pterygoid processes of the wedge-shaped bones of the skull and the inner surface of the corners of the lower jaw.

Lateral pterygoid muscles: the work of these muscles is no less important – they are responsible for opening your mouth, and after you take a bite, for example, of a pie, they help you chew it.

These short, wing-like muscles are located above the medial pterygoid muscles on both sides of the head.

Temporal muscles: similar to large fans, the temporal muscles are located, as you might guess, at the temples and help close the mouth.

Cheek muscles: how is it that we don't bite our cheeks while chewing food? This is due to the fact that the cheek muscles keep them at a safe distance from the teeth.

Chewing muscles (lat. Musculi masticatorii) are the muscles of the head that provide the chewing process.

There are 4 chewing muscles:

Chewing muscle

Temporal muscle

Medial pterygoid muscle

Lateral pterygoid muscle

All of them are attached to the lower jaw. They are also innervated by the trigeminal nerve.

The masticatory, temporal and medial pterygoid muscles, when the mouth is open, attract the lower jaw to the upper one, that is, they close the mouth. With simultaneous contraction of both lateral pterygoid muscles, the lower jaw is pushed forward. The reverse movement of the mandible is produced by the most posterior fibers of the temporal muscle, running almost horizontally from behind to front. If the lateral pterygoid muscle contracts only on one side, then the lower jaw shifts sideways, in the direction opposite to the contracting muscle. The temporal muscle carries out movements of the lower jaw and is also important for articulate speech.

References:

1. M. G. Prives, N. K. Lysenkov, V. I. Bushkovich. Muscles and fascia of the head // Human anatomy. — 11th edition. — St. Petersburg: Hippocrates, 1998. — p. 187. — 704 p.
2. Pivchenko P. G., Trushel N. A., Kovaleva D. V. Anatomy of the musculoskeletal system. A study guide. — 2nd ed. — Minsk: BSMU, 2011. — 147 p. — 552 copies.